

FROM HERE, HEALTH

**An Exposition of Curriculum Rationale: Procedural
Competencies of the Military Physician attached to the Battalion
Aid Station**

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Abstract

Combat casualties can present with a variety of injury patterns and characteristics. The battalion aid station can play a significant role in the care of the injured soldier. Evolving and multifactorial causes may change the type of injuries received at the forward medical facility. The everchanging battlefield scenario makes it essential to review the curriculum of the military physician on a periodic basis. The author undertook a review of scientific articles to understand the incidents, and characteristics of combat related injury and ancillary data. Based upon the results selected procedures have been highlighted in the discussion section. As per the author's view these should be part of the course curriculum for physicians who aspire to serve at the battalion aid station. Some emerging concepts has been touched upon for reflection by interested stakeholders.

An Exposition of Curriculum Rationale: Procedural Competencies of the Military Physician attached to the Battalion Aid Station.

"War is the realm of uncertainty; three quarters of the factors on which action in war is based are wrapped in a fog of greater or lesser uncertainty. A sensitive and discriminating judgment is called for; a skilled intelligence to scent out the truth."- Carl von Clausewitz¹

Introduction

According to recent analyses a substantial portion of deaths in the battlefield are preventable if early interventions are part of the medical management plan.² The battalion aid station (BAS) has often been designated as the Role 2 medical treatment facility (MTF),³ and has served various roles dependent on military doctrines and policies.⁴ Stationed nearest to, but outside the hot zone the BAS is uniquely positioned to serve as the collection point, triaging, stabilisation, and preparation of casualties for further evacuation. The military tactical medic (MTM) may be limited by the extreme threat faced during active combat, and it would be prudent to carry out a further survey of the casualty at the BAS, and implement or modify lifesaving interventions (LSI). The military physician attached to the BAS(MP-BAS) should be conversant in clinical procedures that can be used during LSI towards the objective of stabilisation, and if required the rearward transportation of the casualty to a Role 3 or 4 MTF. The objective of this report is to highlight procedural competencies desirable of an MP-BAS based on review of relevant articles.⁵ Changing technological frameworks,⁶ and shifting geopolitical realities⁷ has long been key factors as to how the combatant is affected by known and unknown opponents, agents and entities. The author has opined on how some of these can impact the delivery of care, and change the injury profiles presenting at the duty station of the MP-BAS.

Methods

A scan for relevant articles using scientific databases was conducted. From an initial pool, articles that enumerated most common combat injury patterns and characteristics were selected. Additionally, articles on resuscitative interventions performed on the combat casualty irrespective of the location, or facility were appraised. Consensus based guidelines, lessons learnt, consortium opinion, and state of courses as applicable to military casualty care was then used to refine the curriculum rationale. Articles that contain data for events and incidents of the last 30 years (1992-2022) has been used. A further exploration of selected emerging concepts has been emphasised to suggest future content enhancement of relevant educational and training endeavours.

Keywords: knowledge gap, tactical medicine, combat medic, battalion aid station, lifesaving interventions, combat trauma registry, tactical curriculum, prehospital battlefield medicine, combat casualty, military physician, technology, third world, future, emerging.

Results

Injury patterns and preventable causes

According to this report⁸ 25% of deaths in the battlefield are preventable. This report⁹ elucidates that vascular injuries are the leading cause of deaths in the battlefield, and about 28% are

noncompressible. The above report mentions that about 73.1 %, of all vascular injuries, were due to explosive rather than penetrative incidents.

Open wounds, fractures and amputations were the major types of battle injury patterns as described in this report.¹⁰ Burns and intracranial injury remained of significant concern. Gunshots, shrapnel fragmentation, explosions, motor vehicle accidents, falls and multimodal mechanisms were the major mechanisms of injury. Acute traumatic coagulopathy(ATC) may develop in cases of severe trauma, during prolonged field care(PFC), or during evacuation.¹¹

Airway obstructions remain the second most common cause, of preventable death, and is mostly due to traumatic disruption of the airway.¹² The majority of casualties had undergone placement of an endotracheal tube(ETT) at a forward semi-fixed facility, or at the rearward hospital. A small portion had undergone extraglottic airway placement, or cricothyroidotomy (CT) during the prehospital phase. Only special operations medics were able to perform timely ETT placement in the prehospital setting. Explosive incidents remain the major mechanism of injury. Airway placement during TFC faces several challenges including poor light, combat chaos, and limited dexterity, which often leads to more surgical airways being performed.¹³ Suctioning has been recommended for better management.

Thoracic injuries form a significant part of the damage sustained, in recent battlegrounds, as reported by this article.¹⁴ Of these a significant portion develop pneumothorax(51.8%), and

haemothorax(30%). Penetrating trauma due to blast injuries remain the commonest cause. A major reclassification, had taken place during the study (2007), leading injuries being classified as either primarily penetrating or blunt.

Abdominal injuries have represented about 7-20% of aggregate combat injuries over the years.¹⁵ The mechanism of injury currently remains divided between gunshot wounds, and blast incidents.¹⁶ Complications include massive haemorrhage, evisceration, bowel perforation, bleeding vessels, and solid organ disruption.

A report¹⁷ has highlighted that head, face and neck injuries (HFNI) constituted about 61% of all injuries at a specific combat theatre over a seven months period. Using the ICD-9-CM codes the findings include nearly the entire range of possible injuries. The most common cause of deaths were open head wounds, and greater survival was noted for isolated facial and neck injuries. Commonest battle related causes included improvised explosive devices (IEDs), mortars, gunshots, and explosives. One notable finding is the occurrence of higher eye injuries by mortars in combatants who were not wearing eye protection.

A report¹⁸ on isolated traumatic brain injury highlights that intracranial pressure monitoring, and some form of operative cranial decompression remained significant interventions, that were performed, in the said cohort.

For certain theatres an unique injury pattern with clustering, known as dismounted complex blast injury(DCMI), has been identified.¹⁹ A re-emergence of multidimensional injury during armoured warfare is garnering interest among researchers.²⁰ Experts predict an increase in burn and inhalation injury, amputations, and TBI for the combatant inside the armoured vehicle.

Significant burns comprise about 5-20% of overall injuries as per statistics,²¹ but seems to consistently contribute to 4% of overall mortality. Explosive devices, have been the main source in certain theatres, and within confined spaces. A principle of prevention, using protective equipment, is being advocated. Tactical burn care with further rearward support seems to have achieved an optimum level, as per studies, for casualties from recent theatres.²²

Discussion

A. Rationale and Identified Procedural Competencies.^{23 24 25}

Several studies have focused on the experiences of our MTM colleagues while on the field, and what challenges they face during imparting tactical care to a wounded soldier.²⁶ Being fired upon, or hit by blast incidents, shrapnel, and flying debris remain the commonest physical threats. The uncontrollable variables such as poor light, resource limitations, foreign and extreme climatic conditions,²⁷ command and control issues, prolonged field evacuation times, and logistical complexities²⁸ add to difficulties in implementing care in an already high threat environment.

To address these uncertainties tactical medicine curriculums²⁹ has focussed on delivering the minimum care based on feasibility models, simulations,³⁰ procedural workshops, and mental

resilience building. Situational awareness, and military doctrines and policies are also stressed upon.³¹

Reviews of LSI done by MTMs during the Care Under Fire (CUF), and Tactical Field Care (TFC) phases are now available.^{32 33} The MP-BAS can have a significant role in battlefield medical care by providing further support, while being relatively protected from the hot zone.³⁴ The chances of a successful procedure increases once the high threat levels, and uncertainties get reduced in the controlled environment setting. Additionally, an early review of procedures, already performed can be judiciously completed.

Priority 1: Control Haemorrhage.

The proper placement of **limb tourniquets**, and the ability to maintain safeguards remains an important priority.³⁵ Additionally, the use of **junctional tourniquets**, has the potential of preventing exsanguination which may have proved difficult to control in the first two phases of tactical medicine.³⁶ Supplementary skills include wound packing, pressure dressing, and haemostatic gauge usage.³⁷

Priority 2: Manage the Airway.

Manoeuvres that open the airway, and prevent blocking remain essential skills. The use of **endotracheal tubes (ETTs)** to establish a definitive airway under controlled settings remains a significant advantage.³⁸ Rapid Sequence Intubation protocols may be used to facilitate placement

of the definitive airway. Additionally, the MP-BAS should be conversant, in establishing an **emergent surgical airway** if all else fails. Placement of **extraglottic airways**,³⁹ Bag Mask Ventilation (BMV) use, and mechanical ventilation configuration and monitoring remain useful ancillary skills.

Priority 3: Breathing.

Needle thoracostomies and finger thoracostomies have been undertaken extensively in the field,⁴⁰ and the MP-BAS may need to assess the casualty to decide on whether a **tube thoracostomy** would be a prudent decision. The said procedure is often undertaken if the casualty is planned for aeromedical evacuation.⁴¹ All chest seals, and drainage systems should be properly evaluated. A thorough inspection of the chest wall is warranted for small or hidden entry wounds.

Priority 4: Circulation.

IO needle placement by the MTM in the field has been demonstrated to be safe, and effective for fluid resuscitation, and has achieved high success rates in maintaining an usable channel.⁴² The MP-BAS may consider **IV access**,^{43 44} or a **central line insertion** via the subclavian, or femoral route as an option for casualties that may require rearward evacuation.⁴⁵ ATC prevention⁴⁶ should focus on principles of damage control resuscitation.⁴⁷

Priority 5: Disability, Exposure issues and Everything else.^{48 49}

Splinting and cervical spine stabilisation would be required in trauma cases. Evisceration and associated injuries would be managed, and reviewed as per TCCC guidelines.⁵⁰ The indications of **pelvic binding, or external fixation** would arise in cases of unstable fractures, and suspected or visible haemorrhage.^{51 52} **Burr hole craniotomy**⁵³ could be a useful addendum for the correct indications based on neurological assessment. **Lateral canthotomy and cantholysis** are indicated in orbital compartment syndrome and is generally carried out at a rearward facility,⁵⁴ but may become necessary during PFC or at the BAS.⁵⁵ Extensive decontamination and burn care may need to be implemented promptly. **Escharotomy** would be indicated in severe and extensive burns. Compartment syndrome may evolve over time and require **fasciotomy**.⁵⁶ **Needle pericardiocentesis** could be given a thought if image guidance is available, but will require training to reduce safety concerns.⁵⁷

B. Major Challenges, Probable Future Trends and Emerging Concepts.⁵⁸

As multiple factors lead to paradigm shifts in combat approaches, and modalities so does the curriculum of battlefield medicine needs to change.⁵⁹ Future Large Scale Combat Operations (LSCO) are predicted to bring forth new challenges, and may force changes in casualty management principles.^{60 61} Proponents of Resuscitative Endovascular Ballon Occlusion of Aorta(REBOA) are touting its feasibility of use by the combat medic, or by the MP who is forward located⁶² though differences of opinion remain.⁶³ Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs/drones) are being given consideration to serve complimentary roles in battlefield medicine.⁶⁴ Specific research groups have come up with priorities for preparation for the next phase of global conflict,^{65 66} and strategic planners are forced to anticipate scenarios which seem

inevitable as of now.⁶⁷ Medical informatics⁶⁸ would probably be integrated with the central informatics system.⁶⁹ Robotic systems⁷⁰ capable of carrying out interventions in the field could become a reality, and has far reaching implications in other spheres, of human activity.⁷¹ Newly introduced weapon systems could change the injury characteristics in not too distant future.⁷²

A study in contrast is the big challenge for economically less developed countries⁷³ to match up to the infrastructure, resource, and technological high ground achieved by superpower/s.⁷⁴

Conclusion⁷⁵

The MP-BAS can provide vital medical support during combat. A relevant curriculum is the essential backbone for courses that aspire to train physicians for this role. The author has tried to identify the preventable causes of death and morbidity due to combat injury, and the required procedural competencies of the relevant clinician. Additional insight can be gained by seeking advisories from firsthand experience holders, subject matter experts, and domain specialists. The next rational step would be to assess the feasibility of required LSI in, and near the hot zone. Curriculum planners should use only those equipment, and instruments that have undergone validation for use in battlefield medical care.⁷⁶ The MP-BAS must still be aware of pertinent limitations based upon his/her knowledge, experience, competence, environmental variables, and situational boundaries.⁷⁷

At the same time taking steps that encourage normalisation of safety, and preventive tactics by the future active combatant can contribute towards reduction in the incidence of injury during training and combat.

Special Note: The author acknowledges his role, and experience as a non-military physician. All referenced articles contain information that has been declassified and deidentified.

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